

Improving the Curriculum Based on Character

Marsella Desriyarini Gui^{1*}, Nurain Kiraman², Mutia Karim³, Fitriyawati Karim⁴, Muthi Muharam⁵, Adelia Mohamad⁶, Ananda Saburi⁷, Minarti Hasan⁸, Nurain Laraka⁹, Ismail Latif¹⁰

Faculty of Teacher Training and Education / Pohuwato University

Corresponding Author: Marsella Desriyarini Gui Marsella1158@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Creating new curricula, changing and improving old curricula, implementing curricula, and supervising basic education curricula is known as character-based curriculum development. Among these controls are curriculum monitoring and assessment and improvement curriculum based on feedback from various basic curriculum assessments and evaluations within and outside educational institutions. Curriculum development must be based on religious principles, Pancasila, culture and national education goals. Consisting of four pillars, these values are organized into eighteen principles: religious, honest, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creative, independent, democratic, national spirit, love for the country, appreciation for achievement, friendship and communication, love of peace, love reading, environmental care, social care, and responsibility

INTRODUCTION

The Latin "karakter", "kharassein", "kharax", and "character" come from the Greek word "charassein", which means to make sharp or deep. According to Danang Prasetyo and Marzuki (2016), character consists of traits, habits, traits and habits. Dharna Kesuma also gives a different definition for the word "character", which means character, morality, morals, affection, morals, character and character.

Genetic and environmental factors influence a person's character involve people who are often around them or influence them, so they start to imitate what they do.

A student at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah, for example, often follows the way his parents, playmates, or even caregivers behave. Because character comes from the process of imitation, namely seeing, hearing, and following, character education can be taught or internalized intentionally through educational activities by creating a character-based curriculum. Thus, it can be concluded that character is a gift from God that is given from birth and is used to interact with the world around us through learning.

Three steps can be taken to build a curriculum based on character education. They are as follows: 1) incorporate value characteristics into all topics, local materials, and self-development activities; 2) improving daily habits at school (administration, education and services); and 3) increasing cooperation between schools, families and communities in developing and understanding the character of values in schools. The national education objectives and the message of the 2003 national education system law serve as the basis for the implementation of character education. The goal is to make students not only smart but also have personality (character), so that the next generation will grow and develop with personalities full of the noble values of Pancasila and religion. Similarly, the Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Graduation Standards (SKL) show that most of the learning outcomes are aimed at developing students' good character values, such as faith and devotion to God, being responsible, honest, and disciplined (Syarifah, 2016).

However, it is clear that the character application approach has not been used well in several schools and Islamic boarding schools. This is because the focus of educational institutions today is to provide students with the knowledge and job skills necessary to compete and survive. However, morality, character and character formation are still given little attention, and education is forgotten, even though it is this character that determines a brighter future. A country regresses because it does not have good character. This is what causes this country to decline and be unable to escape the ongoing multidimensional crisis (Hidayatullah, Furqon, 2007).

LITERATURE REVIEW

For this reason, To produce virtuous students, we must have appropriate and high-quality educational management. : namely graduates who are smart, intelligent, creative, polite and good at communicating, honest, disciplined and have a high sense of responsibility (Aunillah, Nurla Isnam, 2011).

In other words, education must be able to fulfill the goal of character formation so that students and graduates can participate well and successfully in development while maintaining high character values)

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a literature review method to find journals and scientific articles that are relevant to the subject under study (Ibrahim, 2015). The data collected for this research comes from secondary data sources; this is data collected by the researcher from sources other than directly from the subject. Secondary data referred to here is a source of supporting data related to the research subject, which is obtained through literature, books, journals and articles. We as researchers act as a way to obtain the data and information needed for this research. Data recovery, data presentation, and drawing conclusions are three steps that are carried out simultaneously in data analysis (Arikunto, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Definition of Character Based Curriculum Development

The word "development" comes from the root word "kembang", which means "to become more perfect". Then it is encouraged to become a development, process, method or behavior Adibatin, 2016). Therefore, development here is a conscious effort to achieve the goal of becoming more perfect than before. Curriculum is an educational program provided to students by schools. According to (Anam, 2014), this program allows students to carry out various learning activities to encourage their growth and development in accordance with the curriculum. Wayne stated that the character had two meanings. First, the word "morals" refers to behavior. Second, the word "character" is closely related to "personality". A person shows bad morals if they are dishonest, cruel, or greedy, whereas those who are honest and helpful show noble morals. A person can be called a "person of character" if his behavior is in accordance with moral principles. 6 This character is comparable to morality, which comes from the word Khuluk, which means good habits or character. According to Imam al Ghazali (2016), morals are behavior that comes from a good heart. Therefore, developing a character education curriculum is an effort to write or design a new curriculum, change and perfect the curriculum, implement the curriculum, and supervise the basic education curriculum (Arifin, 2014). This control includes control of the basic education curriculum, implementation of the curriculum, changes and improvements to the curriculum, control of the basic education curriculum, and monitoring and evaluation of the curriculum carried out in various school and non-school educational institutions (Ahmadi, 2013).

This control includes monitoring and evaluating the curriculum as well as improving the curriculum based on information from monitoring and evaluation of the basic education curriculum carried out in various school and non-school educational institutions. This control includes controlling the basic education curriculum, implementing the curriculum, changing and perfecting the curriculum, and controlling the basic education curriculum (Defyanti, 2014).

Educational Values Related to National Culture and Character

The following sources show the principles of cultural education and national characteristics (Muthar, 2014).

Religion: People in Indonesia are religious. Therefore, religious teachings and a person's beliefs always determine the lives of individuals, communities and nations. Religion also forms the basis of politics and national character. Therefore, the values of cultural education and national character must be based on religious values and rules.

Pancasila: The principles of national and state life that form the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia are known as Pancasila. Pancasila is mentioned in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution and is explained further in its articles. This means that Pancasila values regulate politics, law, economy, society, arts and culture. Cultural and national character education aims to educate students to become better citizens, namely citizens who have the ability, desire and intention to apply these values in their lives as citizens.

Culture: the fact that society's cultural values determine each person's life. With its important role in people's lives, culture must function as a source of values in cultural education and the formation of national character. These values determine the meaning and significance of a concept in communication between members of society.

Goals Based: National Education Goals are created by various educational institutions at various levels and pathways, and are a formulation of qualities that every Indonesian citizen must have. The goals of national education contain many human values that must be maintained by all Indonesians. Therefore, this goal is the most efficient means for developing cultural education and national character. Contribute, send feedback to the side panel, save it, and provide information.

Curriculum Creation Goal Based on Character Education

As we already know, humans were created equipped various potentials that must be developed, so that these potentials are in accordance with the function created by humans themselves, namely as representatives of Allah SWT in order to preserve nature (Fathurrohman, 2007).

So, character formation is a necessity and even the goal of education. As mentioned in a Hadith, the Prophet Muhammad SAW was sent to an ignorant society with the aim of improving morals. In Islam, character education (morals) emphasizes the formation of good attitudes and behavior for each person so that they can do good for themselves and their community.

According to Aminah Ahmad Hasan, the relationship between individuals and Islamic society is defined as "il_qah rūhiyyah khuluqiyah", or interactions bound by a code of ethics. Therefore, there are many ways to shape a child's character. Apart from the methods mentioned above, the following approaches can be used to shape children's character (Budimansyah, 2012):

1. Eligibility

The attitudes and behavior that are exemplified come from the deepest conscience, so that the actions taken do not deviate from God's will and community standards. Allah uses examples or example as the best model to teach humans. This makes education easy for humans to accept and apply. Therefore, example is the most effective educational method for building children's character. For example, in the family, parents must be good role models for their children, and in schools, teachers must be role models in all things for their children. What is taught to students will only be theory without examples (Rusman, 2015). Therefore, the teacher's example in his activities will reflect that of his students. Islamic teachers must be emulated by their students.

2. Cultivation of habits

Amiroeddin Sjarif stated that discipline is basically real obedience which is supported by awareness of fulfilling duties and obligations and behaving in accordance with the code of conduct that should apply in a particular environment. Therefore, there are values that determine whether someone actually does something or not because of discipline in carrying out rules in the environment or activities carried out regularly. The discipline imposed is an effort to change a person's character (Darmayanti, S., E. & Wibowo, U., B., 2014).
Separation

Children will grow and develop as their environment teaches them and the habits they do every day. A child will grow up to be a perpetrator of violence if their environment teaches them good habits, but if their environment teaches them to do evil or violence, then they will get used to committing crimes in the future (Wahyudin, 2016).

3. Create a Friendly Atmosphere

A good atmosphere will facilitate character formation. Therefore, many things related to character building efforts must be conditioned, especially people who are currently in that service.

Schools must create a topic network with character values for each subject, local content material, and self-development so that character education works well (Mustari, Mohamad. 2011). To support character education, madrasah management must be conditioned to support character education activities. Character values must be applied in madrasa facilities. For example, the madrasah looks neat, learning tools are placed in an orderly manner, rubbish bins are in various places and are always cleaned, the prayer room or prayer room is suitable for congregational midday prayers and congregational midday prayers, and there are also religious reading facilities such as the Al-Quran, Juz Amma, and translation. To achieve character education, it is very important to maintain the principle of openness in school management and services. For example, the principal must always talk to all teachers about the school's work program,

Madrasah financial reports, and other things. Apart from that, teachers must instill the principle of openness to all their students, both in class and in extracurricular activities.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

To control the basic education curriculum and create a new curriculum, it is said to develop a character-based curriculum. This control includes curriculum improvements based on assessment and monitoring information obtained from the assessment and evaluation of different basic curricula that have been implemented inside and outside educational institutions. Education must be based on religious principles, Pancasila, culture and national education goals. One of the 18 values derived from the four pillars is religious, honest, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creative, independent, democratic, curiosity, love of nationality, respect for achievement, friendship or communication, peace, likes to read, cares for the environment, social care, and responsibility. There are four approaches used to develop a character-based curriculum, namely: 1. Modeling, 2. Instilling discipline, 3. Habituation, and 4. Creating a friendly environment.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Improving the Curriculum Based On Character in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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